

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

After two fat issues here is a slim one, for a change! However, although it only contains three papers they are typical for J.UCS as far as the variety of topics is concerned. From the current state of submissions the same will be true for the August issue. However, three more (!) special issues are in preparation, and at least one of them should be ready before the end of this year.

For today: happy reading, have a nice summer (winter skiing down under!), and don't forget to send your next good paper to J.UCS.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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PS: I still have CD ROM's with volume 1 of J.UCS (all papers of 95)...if interested in such a CD, just send me an email to hmaurer@iicm.edu. The printed archival version of J.UCS is also in its final stages. It has the ISSN number 0948-695X and will cost DM 298.-